

INTEGRATING SEISMIC STRENGTHENING AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY FOR BUILDING RENOVATION: BIO-BASED INSULATION, BIPV, AND STRUCTURAL RETROFITS FOR MINIMAL DISRUPTION

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Abstract

The aging European building stock presents a significant challenge, as a substantial share of buildings in seismic-prone regions do not match modern seismic standards. The European Green Deal promotes building renovation to enhance energy efficiency while ensuring seismic safety. However, while energy retrofitting is widely applied, seismic strengthening is less common mainly due to the disruption it causes to occupants. This study introduces an innovative renovation approach integrating seismic and energy upgrades with minimal disruption. The proposed method strengthens exterior beam-column joints while enhancing the envelope's thermal and energy performance using bio-based insulation panels and Building-Integrated Photovoltaic (BIPV) cladding. Acting only from outside, the need to relocate residents during renovations is reduced. The approach is tested in a social housing case study in Margherita di Savoia, Italy, as an initiative part of the Horizon Europe REHOUSE project, which aims to provide scalable and sustainable renovation solutions across the EU. The combined intervention enhances seismic resilience and energy efficiency while addressing socio-economic and environmental challenges through a reduced disruption and the use of sustainable materials. Results show that seismic upgrades based on carbon fibre-reinforced polymer (CFRP) led to a five-fold increase in seismic safety with a competitive cost. Energy efficiency, by reducing thermal transmittance, has led to a considerable reduction in the building's energy demand. Additionally, the photovoltaic integration on the building facades will meet the demand for electricity to run the heat pumps.

Keywords: Seismic and Energy Upgrades for Residential Building, Bio-Based Insulation, BIPV, Low-Disruption Retrofits

1 INTRODUCTION

The existing European building stock predates the adoption of rigorous seismic codes. At the same time, it is essential to consider integrated EU initiatives like REPowerEU, the Renovation Wave and, the New European Bauhaus, all of which are driving sustainable transformation across the EU. 40% of the European Union (EU) buildings are in seismic-prone regions and were built without modern seismic design considerations [1]. It brings a significant design gap with respect to modern seismic standards. The further aging of the building stock, combined with the renovation requests led by the European Union through the Green Deal, calls for a building renovation. Ensuring seismic safety is a key principle of the Green Deal, which emphasizes high health and environmental standards. This initiative is further supported by the New European Bauhaus, which aims to create sustainable, inclusive, and beautiful living spaces. The importance of a sustainable use of resources and energy efficiency is the key, as buildings account for approximately 40% of total energy consumption in the European Union [2]. Building-Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV) play a crucial role in energy renovation, seamlessly merging renewable energy generation with building design [3].

This makes the building sector a crucial target for reducing carbon emissions and enhancing safety and sustainability to avoid that, in case of a seismic event, after the only energy renovation, the risk of occupants remains the same, but the economic losses are enhanced [3].

Despite its importance, the application of technologies related to seismic renovation remains limited compared to energy-related renovations on the building. Furthermore, existing seismic renovation technologies often lack cost-effectiveness and result in inconvenience to residents who are forced to evacuate the building during seismic renovations. Recent studies have proposed various common renovation technologies for masonry and reinforced concrete (RC) buildings [4, 5].

In response, this paper introduces an innovative approach to the deep renovation of residential buildings, emphasizing the enhancement of seismic safety and resilience by reinforcing exterior beam-column joints. This structural improvement can be accompanied by energy efficiency measures on the building envelope with the use of materials derived from natural sources and renewable energy production through building-integrated photovoltaics. The combined seismic and energy efficiency strategies are designed as exterior-only interventions to minimize disruption for residents. Given their socio-economic vulnerabilities, this approach is especially advantageous for social housing, where it is vital to reduce the need for residents to relocate during renovations. The combined intervention strategy is being demonstrated in a case study of a building located in a social housing neighbourhood in Margherita di Savoia, a small town in southern Italy. The multipurpose façade prioritizes environmental sustainability by using mechanical steel fasteners instead of silicone adhesives and incorporating bio-based insulation panels. This initiative is part of the Horizon Europe research project called REHOUSE (Renovation packagEs for HOlistic improvement of EU's bUildingS Efficiency, maximizing RES generation and cost-effectiveness) [6].

This comprehensive renovation methodology provides a scalable and sustainable solution for upgrading existing residential buildings, especially in seismic-prone regions, while enhancing energy efficiency and enabling the decentralized generation of solar power. It prioritizes safety while also promoting environmental and social sustainability. By focusing exclusively on exterior interventions, this approach tackles a major barrier to renovations: the need to relocate tenants during the construction process.

In this paper, the subject of this study is the Italian demonstration building developed in the Rehouse project, for which the seismic and energy upgrading interventions are designed,

realized, and monitored during the service life. The following sections describe the design choices, the upgrading foreseen results, and the plan to monitor the system performance over time.

The following chapters will first present the seismic assessment of the building under study, followed by a detailed description of the seismic retrofitting approach adopted and its advantages. Subsequently, the proposed energy efficiency measures for the demonstration site will be outlined, including details on the materials used and the type of intervention implemented. The objective is to demonstrate that energy efficiency improvements should be accompanied by seismic upgrades to maximize overall benefits and enhance the resilience of the built environment.

2 SEISMIC ASSESSMENT

The Italian Demonstration Site Building, also referred to as "Building A", is a reinforced concrete social housing unit designed in the early 1980s (Figure 1a). It is located in Margherita di Savoia, in the province of Barletta-Andria-Trani (Apulia region), within the Capitanata area, known for its high social vulnerability [7]. The building is built in a suburban setting, between saltworks to the southwest and the sea to the northeast. Information about its geometry, material properties and reinforcement layout was obtained from design documents provided by ARCA Capitanata, the building's owner.

The structure has a rectangular layout (22×11 m) and consists of four residential floors plus a terrace level. Its foundations are composed of a reinforced concrete plate stiffened by beams. The load-bearing system consists of reinforced concrete frames arranged in two main directions, supporting cementitious screed floor slabs (Figure 1b). An elevator shaft is positioned along the long side of the building, adjacent to the staircase. The design was completed in 1984, and static load testing was carried out in 1986. The structural design considered seismic actions according to the 1981 classification of Margherita di Savoia.

Figure 1: View of the Italian Demonstration Building (a) and BIM model (b).

The structural system features wide beams, with a depth smaller than the width. Floor slabs consist of reinforced concrete T-shaped joists with hollow clay blocks, forming a total thickness of 24 cm (20 cm for joists and 4 cm for the top layer reinforced with a steel net), making the floor diaphragms rigid for in-plane actions. The total building area is 220 m², with an inter-story height of 3 m. The main structural elements are made of R'_{bk} 250-grade concrete, with a cubic compressive strength of 25 MPa, and FeB44K reinforcing steel, which has a characteristic

yielding stress of 430 MPa. Column dimensions are typically 70×25 cm, while beam dimensions vary: 100×24 cm for perimeter beams, and 70×24 cm or 50×24 cm for internal ones. A few beams near the plan centre have a depth greater than their width (30×60 cm). No records of structural modifications over time were found.

The external envelope walls consist of a single layer of perforated clay blocks (37 cm thick) with an additional 15 mm thick plaster layer on both sides. The clay blocks are placed externally, aligning with the beam edges to reduce thermal bridges. The columns are covered by 8 cm thick hollow clay bricks. The lower part of the building features additional aesthetic cladding, including 80 mm thick perforated bricks and a 20 mm marble layer. Heating systems in the apartments are independent, with natural gas boilers, and three units are equipped with heat pumps for heating and cooling. More details on energy systems are available in the energy audit section.

The structural and seismic assessment was performed using finite element analysis following the Italian building code. The assumed material properties for calculations included a mean concrete compressive strength of 26.8 MPa and a mean steel tensile strength of 430 MPa. These values are derived from an extensive in-situ testing campaign according to a Knowledge Level 2 (KL2) [7, 8]. The assessment procedure involved:

- Static load analysis to verify structural members' capacity under gravity loads;
- Damage Limitation (DL) state assessment under frequent earthquakes to ensure inter-story drift remained within 0.5% of the story height, preserving non-structural elements like infill walls and newly installed systems;
- Life Safety (LS) state assessment under less frequent earthquakes to evaluate the risk of structural failure.

The static analysis confirmed that all structural elements had a demand-capacity ratio below 1.0, meaning no component reached its full load-bearing capacity. This result suggests that invasive reinforcement interventions are unnecessary for gravity load resistance.

For the damage limitation check, the analysis verified that the maximum inter-floor drift did not exceed the threshold required to protect non-structural elements. The maximum inter-story drift ratio was found to be 4.95%, within the 5% limit set by the Italian code. The highest displacement occurred at the second story, but no additional stiffening interventions were required.

At the life safety limit state, the building exhibited vulnerability to shear failure, particularly in beam-column joints, a common issue in older reinforced concrete buildings. A linear dynamic analysis was performed by gradually increasing seismic forces until the first failure occurred. The results showed that the building, in its current state, could only withstand 10% ($\zeta_{LS} = 0.1$) of the design seismic action before critical shear failure appeared in two beam-column joints and one column (Figure 2a). For a fully compliant structure, the seismic safety index should be at least 1.0.

To explore possible retrofitting strategies, the seismic force was progressively increased. At 50% of the design seismic action ($\zeta_{LS} = 0.5$), seventeen joints and six columns experienced shear failure. Without refining the assessment criteria, as illustrated in the safety check methodology [7], the number of failed joints would have been 63, leading to overly conservative retrofit solutions.

Beyond 50% of the design seismic action, flexural failure began to occur in beams and columns, indicating the need for extensive and intrusive interventions. However, by focusing on strengthening beam-column joints and a few key columns in the staircase area, the seismic safety index could reach 0.5, which represents a viable retrofit strategy. Importantly, all failing joints are located on the building façade, allowing reinforcement work to be carried out externally with minimal disruption to residents.

Figure 2: Safety checks of beam–column joints and columns for $\zeta_{LS} = 0.1$ (a) and $\zeta_{LS} = 0.5$ front façade (b) and rear façade (c).

3 DESIGN OF THE SEISMIC UPGRADING INTERVENTION

Beam column joints in reinforced concrete buildings often require strengthening due to aging, increased loads, environmental damage, or seismic retrofitting, as in this case. One of the most effective and minimally invasive techniques for reinforcing these joints involves using fibre-reinforced composite materials, such as carbon fibre fabrics, combined with epoxy resins and high-performance bonding agents. The use of carbon fibre-reinforced polymer (CFRP) materials represents an effective solution that combines increased seismic performance with ease of installation, resulting in reduced time and costs [9, 10, 11]

This method allows for interventions to be carried out entirely from the outside, eliminating the need for invasive demolition or major structural modifications. Moreover, the thickness required by these techniques is very small due to the minimal volume of involved materials.

Experimental and analytical studies conducted in recent years have led to the development of guidelines [12, 13, 14] and design formulations [16] to support engineers in defining the most suitable intervention methods and the appropriate amount of reinforcement required to structural elements. As a result, these strengthening systems have become one of the most commonly used techniques for the seismic improvement of existing reinforced concrete buildings [17], as often observed in post-earthquake reconstruction processes following recent seismic events [16, 17].

Figure 3 illustrates the strengthening process of a reinforced concrete joint using carbon fibre-reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites. The intervention begins with an assessment of the existing reinforced concrete joint, followed by the restoration of any damaged areas using

a high-strength, thixotropic fibre-reinforced mortar. This step ensures the joint's integrity before applying the CFRP system, all while working externally without suspend the structure's internal functionality.

Next, an epoxy resin primer is applied to the concrete surface to enhance adhesion. A bidirectional carbon fibre fabric is then placed externally around the joint, covering both the beams and the column to provide confinement and increase the load-bearing capacity. Depending on the design requirements, multiple layers of fabric can be applied, always externally, ensuring a rapid and non-intrusive strengthening process. A second epoxy resin layer is then spread to fully impregnate the fibre and create a strong bond with the concrete.

Figure 3: Features and working phases of beam-column joints' strengthening intervention (adapted from [20]).

To further adhesion, a layer of spherical quartz is added, allowing for better integration with subsequent protective coatings. The process is completed with the application of a fine fibre-reinforced mortar, which provides a smooth, durable finish while protecting the reinforcement. This final step maintains the aesthetic and functional integrity of the structure without requiring significant alterations.

A key feature of this intervention is the use of carbon fibre anchors, which are bonded into small holes drilled externally into the beams and columns. These anchors improve the load transfer between the CFRP reinforcement and the existing concrete, preventing premature debonding and enhancing the overall effectiveness of the strengthening solution.

This method is particularly advantageous in seismic retrofitting and structural rehabilitation projects, as it offers a high-strength, lightweight solution with minimal disruption to the existing structure. Since all phases of the intervention can be performed externally, it is ideal for situations where maintaining the building's operational use is crucial, such as in bridges, public buildings, and critical infrastructure.

The design of CFRP reinforcement involves determining the number of composite material layers to be applied to the joint to enhance its strength in terms of principal tensile stress, as specified in [9].

For the interventions on the Margherita di Savoia building "JOINT FRP", an analytical tool provided by [21] to assist engineers during the design of reinforcement systems for reinforced concrete beam-column joints by composite materials was used. The software enables the optimization of resources and materials based on predefined objectives and allows the integration of innovative anchorage systems that facilitate external-only reinforcement applications. It can be employed for local strengthening or global retrofit and has been validated through experimental tests on full-scale multi-story frames.

The design methodology implemented in the software follows the approach of the fib Bulletin 90 [15], whose calibration procedure, performed using a database of experimental tests on unconfined FRP-strengthened joints, is detailed in [16]. This approach, once the reinforcement scheme, material type, fabric characteristics, geometric and mechanical properties and number of layers have been defined, allows for the assessment of the increase in principal tensile stress in the joint panel due to the FRP reinforcement, $p_{t,f}$. This contribution is added to the concrete's inherent resistance, assumed as $0.3\sqrt{f_c}$.

The principal tensile stress that the FRP reinforcement can sustain is determined using the following equation (1):

$$p_{t,f} = \frac{\varepsilon_{f,d} \times E_f \times A_f}{\left(b_c \times \frac{h_c}{\sin\vartheta}\right)} \quad (1)$$

where $\varepsilon_{f,d}$ is the design strain of the composite, which can be calculated using the following expression (2):

$$\varepsilon_{f,d} = \min \left\{ \varepsilon_{f,u}; 34 \left(\frac{f_{cm}^{2/3}}{A_f E_f} \right)^{0.6} \right\} \quad (2)$$

The value of the strain $\varepsilon_{f,u}$ is defined in [14]. This expression has been calibrated through experimental tests, accounting for various uncertainties and ensuring compliance with the safety requirements recommended by [22]. Safety factors are already incorporated into the model coefficient, eliminating the need for additional partial coefficients or confidence factors.

E_f represents the elastic modulus of the CFRP fabric, while A_f is the equivalent area of the CFRP reinforcement. The latter is evaluated based on the arrangement of the fabric fibers relative to the horizontal axis of the joint. In this case study, a biaxial fabric was chosen, and the formula for calculating the reinforcement fabric area is reported in equation (3) according to [15]:

$$A_f = n_s \times n_l \times t_f \times h_c \times \cos\theta \times (1 + (\tan\theta)^2) \quad (3)$$

where: n_s represents the number of sides of the shear-reinforced panel (equal to 1 if there is a converging beam in the joint in the orthogonal direction, otherwise equal to 2); n_l represents the number of reinforcement layers; t_f is the equivalent thickness of the dry CFRP fabric; h_c is the height of the column section; $\vartheta = \arctan(h_b/h_j)$; h_b is the height of the converging beam section in the joint; h_j is the height of the joint section.

The strength verification of the CFRP-reinforced system is conducted by considering the system's capacity as the sum of the tensile capacity provided by both the concrete and the CFRP reinforcement, as reported in equation (4).

$$\sigma_{jt,FRP} = 0.3 \times \sqrt{f_{cd}} + p_{t,f} \geq \sigma_{jt} \quad (4)$$

The tensile force within the joint panel (σ_{jt}) is calculated as a function of the joint shear (V_j) and the normal force (N) acting at the base of the upper column (A_j), as reported in expression (5).

$$\sigma_{jt} = \left| \frac{N}{2A_j} - \sqrt{\left(\frac{N}{2A_j}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{V_j}{2A_j}\right)^2} \right| \quad (5)$$

The shear demand in the joint (V_j) is evaluated using the following equation (6) according to [8]:

$$V_j = V_{jbd} = \gamma_{Rd}(A_{S1} + A_{S2}) \times \sigma_s - V_c \quad (6)$$

where: AS_1 and AS_2 are the areas of the upper and lower reinforcement in the left and right beam sections converging in the joint; γ_{Rd} is the safety factor; σ_s is the steel stress; V_c is the shear force in the column above the joint. Both σ_s and V_c are evaluated in the post-intervention condition ($\zeta_{LS} = 0.5$).

To anchor the CFRP reinforcement, high-strength carbon fiber connectors are provided, housed in dedicated holes within the reinforced concrete elements. These connectors ensure the anchorage of the reinforcement to the joint, operating externally without requiring the demolition of any portion of the infill.

In accordance with failure mechanisms, commonly observed in anchorage systems made of stone materials [23] and based on experimental tests where the connector was subjected orthogonally to its insertion axis [24], the resistance of each connector is evaluated based on the following failure modes:

Concrete cone detachment (N_{cc});

Mixed failure due to concrete cone detachment and bond (N_{cb});

Anchor pull-out (N_{po});

Delamination at the interface between the connector and the FRP fabric (N_{sd});

Fiber shearing of the connector (V_{fr}).

The anchorage resistance (N_{min}) is the minimum value among the resistances listed above, as reported in expression (7).

$$N_{min} = \min (N_{cc}, N_{cb}, N_{po}, N_{sd}, V_{fr}) \quad (7)$$

Therefore, the number of anchors to be placed on each converging beam in the joint, necessary to transmit the effective working stress of the composite while preventing failure due to end delamination of the CFRP reinforcement system, is determined as V_{max}/N_{min} , where V_{max} is calculated with expression (8).

$$V_{max} = A_{eq} \times E_f \times \varepsilon_{f,d} \quad (8)$$

The number of anchors to be placed on the columns is assumed to be equal to that required for the beams, distributed among the number of columns converging in the joint.

For the six stairwell columns (Figure 2b), a CFRP shear reinforcement system is designed to increase the shear capacity in each critical section at $\zeta_{LS} = 0.5$. The shear deficit is compensated by applying a single wrap of unidirectional CFRP fabric, with a thickness (s) of 0.21 mm, bonded orthogonally to the column axis (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Features and working phases of column strengthening intervention (adapted from [20]).

The shear strength of each reinforced element is calculated by summing the shear capacity of the unreinforced element, evaluated in accordance with [8], and the shear-tensile capacity of the composite. The shear-tensile capacity of the composite is added to the contribution of the transverse reinforcement. In all cases, the strength of the reinforced element does not exceed the shear-compression capacity of the concrete.

In this case, assuming that the CFRP reinforcement is applied as a continuous wrap on elements with a rectangular section, the contribution of the CFRP reinforcement system ($V_{Rd,f}$) is evaluated based on the Mörsh truss mechanism [14] using the following expression (9):

$$V_{Rd,f} = \frac{1}{\gamma_{Rd}} f_{fed} \times A_{fv} \times \frac{0.9d}{p_f} (\cot\theta + \cot\beta) \sin\beta \quad (9)$$

where d is the effective height of the section;

f_{fed} is the effective design strength of the reinforcement system;

$A_{fv} = 2t_f \times b_f$ is the area of the shear-resistant fiber stirrup made with externally applied strips on the reinforced concrete section;

p_f is the spacing of the strips, measured orthogonally to the fiber direction; $b_f/p_f = 1$ for continuous strips;

$\gamma_{Rd} = 1.2$ is the partial coefficient; $\theta = 45^\circ$ is the crack inclination angle;

$\beta = 90^\circ$ is the angle of fiber inclination with respect to the beam axis.

The external intervention strategy, which involves the local reinforcement of only 17 joints and 6 columns using CFRP fiber-reinforced materials, led to an approximately 400% increase in the seismic capacity of the structure. The total cost of the intervention is estimated at approximately 66 €/m², including structural work and restoration of building finishes.

This result is consistent with recent research studies on existing buildings within Italy's residential and public building stock [25, 26]. These studies provide a technical and economic comparison of different local and global intervention strategies for the seismic retrofit of reinforced concrete frame structures (Table 1).

DEMO building REHOUSE	1960s school building	
$\zeta_{SLV} = 0.10$ (as-built)	$\zeta_{SLV} = 0.12$ (as-built)	
 (c)		
Retrofit by CFRP on 17 joints and 6 columns	Retrofit by CFRP on 33 joints and 6 beams	Retrofit by dissipative exoskeleton
$\zeta_{SLV} = 0.50$ (post-retrofit)	$\zeta_{SLV} = 0.60$ (post-retrofit)	$\zeta_{SLV} = 0.60$ (post-retrofit)
Intervention cost 66 €/m ²	Intervention cost 78 €/m ²	Intervention cost 277 €/m ²

Table 1: Case studies of the Project Rehouse (a) and Project DPC-RELUIS 21 (b,c).

Choosing a global intervention strategy, such as an exoskeleton attached to the existing structure [27], would result in a significant increase in costs (Table 1, figure c) while achieving

the same level of seismic performance. Moreover, this highly intrusive architectural solution would be less compatible with the energy efficiency system proposed in this article, which will be discussed in the next section.

4 ENERGY EFFICIENCY INTERVENTIONS

4.1 Reduction of energy consumption in buildings

European Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) [28] is the primary policy tool to address this challenge for new and existing buildings. According to the EPBD, all new buildings must be nearly zero-energy buildings (NZEB) as of 2021 (public buildings as of 2019). Related regulations, including the Ecodesign Directive, the Energy Labelling Regulation, and the Energy Efficiency Directive complement the EPBD. Despite the introduction of minimum energy performance requirements, today new buildings consume only half as much energy as those built in the 1980s. While tools such as Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) create a market-driven demand for energy-efficient buildings and provide recommendations for energy retrofits, energy renovation targets must extend beyond new constructions to include the renovation and modernization of the existing building stock [29].

It is essential to highlight and emphasize the multiple benefits of BIPV in architectural designs, economic viability, and digital design benefits [3]. Developers can offer modern, architecturally refined structures, enhancing productivity and competitiveness while also creating jobs and improving energy security for the public [30]. Additionally, occupants benefit from lower energy bills and improved living conditions due to enhanced indoor comfort. A better quality of life for residents often translates into improved social conditions. Successfully implementing energy renovation projects requires not only technical expertise but also a practical understanding of social innovation, integrating societal needs and ideas into technological projects. In the Horizon Europe program [31], social innovation plays a key role in addressing societal challenges and mitigating the risks of inadequate approaches. Supporting social innovation is essential to overcoming regulatory and cultural barriers. When integrated with technological innovation, it facilitates the adoption of new solutions, promotes behavioural changes, and enhances the overall impact of building renovations.

4.2 Multi-Purpose Facades with seismic retrofitting for Resilient and Sustainable Buildings

Seismic retrofitting is a fundamental step in ensuring the structural resilience of buildings, protecting lives, and minimizing the risk of collapse during earthquakes. Prioritizing seismic strengthening before implementing energy efficiency upgrades is both a safety necessity and an economically viable approach. Addressing seismic vulnerabilities first prevents potential rework or damage to newly installed energy efficiency measures, ultimately reducing costs. Additionally, combining seismic and energy retrofitting leads to more comprehensive and efficient renovations, aligning with sustainability goals and regulatory requirements while extending building lifespan and minimizing long-term repair needs.

A key innovation in energy retrofitting is the multi-purpose facade (MPF), an evolution of External Thermal Insulation Composite Systems (ETICS). MPFs not only enhance thermal insulation but also integrate additional functionalities such as acoustic insulation and renewable energy generation through photovoltaic modules. These systems contribute to reducing CO₂ emissions, optimizing energy consumption, and improving overall building performance. The modular design and prefabrication of MPFs allow for rapid on-site assembly, minimizing

disruptions during renovations. Their adaptability makes them suitable for a wide range of buildings, ensuring customized solutions while improving installation efficiency.

Beyond energy performance, MPFs can play a critical role in seismic retrofitting. The integration of steel exoskeletons within MPFs has demonstrated significant improvements in seismic resistance, increasing lateral load capacity by up to 100% in certain cases [32]. This innovative approach enables holistic building upgrades by simultaneously enhancing structural integrity and energy efficiency. Moreover, incorporating circular and bio-based materials in MPFs supports sustainability by reducing environmental impact, promoting recyclability, and preserving valuable resources. Designing fastening systems that facilitate material reuse can further contribute to reducing construction waste and fostering a circular economy.

4.3 Innovative envelope technologies

The Margherita of Savoia demonstration site operates at Technology Readiness Level (TRL) 7, meaning that it represents a system prototype demonstration in an operational environment. The products used in this project are not yet market-ready but will be installed and evaluated under real-world conditions to identify challenges and potential improvements for future large-scale implementation. The natural hemp insulation panels are designed for simple and rapid installation, ensuring efficiency during construction. Likewise, the photovoltaic glass cladding has been developed with optimized dimensions and weight of the panels to facilitate installation and replacement in case of malfunction (Figure 5). Along with speeding up the installation process, this system will greatly reduce the requirement for additional equipment. Most of the work will be conducted externally, limiting disruptions for residents throughout the renovation.

Figure 5: Representation of the MPF module: 1) insulation; 2) substructure; 3) window frame; 4) wall casing; 5) BIPV; 6) facing [33].

The multi-purpose facade was designed as a ventilated facade, integrating innovative thermal insulation and an active cladding system that generates energy through photovoltaic glass panels. The modular prefabricated MPF facade system consists of 31 distinct elements, each serving a specific function. The new building envelope can be categorized into three main components:

- Structural exoskeleton;
- Natural hemp insulation panels;
- PV cladding system.

For non-photovoltaic finishing areas, where technical constraints prevent the use of solar panels, prefabricated fibre cement panels from “Equitone” [34] will be installed.

From a sustainability perspective, most materials used in the MPF are recyclable, either in their original form or through modification. This supports the project's eco-friendly objectives and significantly reduces the environmental impact at the end of the materials' lifecycle.

From an energy efficiency standpoint, the building skin insulation favours the use of low-temperature heat pump systems for indoor climate control. By reducing heat dispersion, the system will decrease operating hours and overall energy consumption. Additionally, the integration of laminated photovoltaic glass modules will provide on-site energy production sufficient to cover the annual energy demand of the heat pumps.

In the following sections, the key components of the MPF will be analysed in detail, highlighting their characteristics and benefits.

4.3.1. Structural Exoskeleton

The installation concept of the modular MPF facade operates similarly to a plug-and-play system for building envelopes. This approach allows the new facade to be installed over the existing structure without the need to remove the original cladding (Figure 6). The system serves multiple functions, including:

- Enhanced thermal insulation;
- Improved acoustic performance;
- Integration of photovoltaic panels within the building envelope.

Figure 6: MPF Modules and brackets system installation [33].

The exoskeleton also referred to as the substructure, consists of the anchoring system required to support both the insulation panels and photovoltaic modules. It is composed of a set of structural profiles and connectors that establish a secure link between the existing wall, the new structural framework, and the insulating and finishing materials of the facade.

Ensuring seamless structural integration with the existing building is essential to support the additional loads imposed by the modular system, such as its weight and wind pressure. A comprehensive load-bearing capacity assessment of the existing structure is a key aspect of the facade's design, helping to determine the optimal connection points for anchoring.

The anchoring system is also designed to accommodate irregularities in the existing facade, ensuring adaptability across different building conditions. A specialized fastening system has been developed, featuring brackets that attach to the building's structure and support the suspended facade modules. This system ensures that photovoltaic and fibrocement panels remain perfectly aligned, both for aesthetic reasons and to prevent shading or uneven surfaces that could negatively impact energy production.

The anchoring system allows for three-dimensional adjustments between the building structure and the facade modules, ensuring compliance with tolerance requirements and enabling precise corrections along the X and Y axes. In particular, horizontal adjustments are provided by the anchoring components, and bidimensional fine-tuning and levelling are managed through the integrated anchoring mechanism within the modules.

This design ensures that panels can be adjusted to compensate for irregularities in the underlying support, allowing precise positioning corrections in two directions. The adjustable mounting system significantly streamlines installation, enabling the rapid and efficient assembly of large facade sections. As a result, on-site renovation time is reduced, minimizing disruptions for residents during the construction phase.

4.3.2. Natural hemp insulation panels

Thermal insulation plays a crucial role in minimizing the environmental impact of the construction sector by reducing the energy demand for heating and cooling. For the renovation of the building's facade, a bio-based hemp fibre insulation solution — Biomat MULTI DENSITY — was selected. This material provides high-performance thermal and acoustic insulation, along with exceptional moisture regulation and hygrothermal balancing properties.

The decision to use hemp insulation was driven by its outstanding environmental benefits. Hemp absorbs approximately 325 kg of CO₂ per ton, actively produces oxygen, and contributes to the preservation of biodiversity in the areas where it is cultivated.

The hemp-based insulation layer is designed as a multi-density, stratified panel, with progressively increasing density from the inner to the outer surface.

This composition enhances:

- Seamless compatibility with standard fastening systems;
- Superior impact resistance;
- Long-term durability.

Additionally, the facade system integrates a ventilated cavity between the photovoltaic cladding and the insulation material, improving both thermal performance and moisture control for both PV elements and the building envelope. Depending on specific project requirements, the system thickness can range between 20 and 35 cm. In terms of energy efficiency, the system achieves U-values below 0.2 W/m²K (Figure 5).

At the Margherita di Savoia pilot site, the facade stratigraphy consists of a 167 mm cross-section, incorporating the fastening system, the hemp panel for the insulation, the ventilated air gap for the airflow, and the external finish composed of glass photovoltaic modules. The achieved overall thermal transmittance (U-value) is 0.27 W/m²K, closely aligning with the reference parameter of 0.26 W/m²K established in the project requirements.

Table 2 presents the key performance indicator for the RP#5 renovation package, comparing the calculated U-value after intervention with the baseline value before the renovation. It is important to note that, as the intervention has not yet been implemented, this performance value is derived from analytical design calculations rather than field measurements.

With the refurbishment, and applying the MPF technology, the improvement in the U-value will be around 70% significantly contributing to the building's overall energy efficiency.

RP#5	Calculate value	Baseline value (before renovation)	Kpi (project value)	Improvement %
MPF	0.27 W/m ² K	0.94 Phase shift:10.53 h	0.26 W/m ² K	71%

Table 2: Insulation against standards (W/m²K) [33].

4.3.3. PV integrated cladding system

The energy-active cladding system integrates opaque BIPV (Building-Integrated Photovoltaic) panels, optimized to reduce both production time and costs while meeting architectural, energy, and construction requirements. The photovoltaic glass panels, named SUNCOL® [35], strike an optimal balance between aesthetics and efficiency. The SUNCOL PUZZLE series features three primary module sizes, specifically designed to adapt to a variety of facade configurations where different panel dimensions are required. These modules are engineered to be lightweight, ensuring easy handling and fast installation. Their coloured surface discreetly conceals the active photovoltaic elements, achieving a 24% efficiency rate.

A key advantage of these coloured PV modules is the design flexibility they offer architects, allowing for customized colours and finishes. This feature ensures that BIPV facades can seamlessly blend with different architectural styles while preserving creative freedom. For the Margherita di Savoia building, a red-toned cladding was chosen from a palette of six different colours, harmonizing with the local architectural language and surrounding landscape. Additionally, fibre cement bands were incorporated to reflect traditional local construction techniques (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Mock-up developed with SUNCOL PUZZLE and with fibre cement.

The mounting system, featuring rear-attached rail profiles positioned on both small edges, will be undergoing testing and validation at the demonstration site under real-world conditions.

The system consists of two main profiles which can be arranged in various configurations to ensure precise BIPV module alignment on the façade. This innovative mechanical fastening solution significantly reduces the use of adhesives, enhancing the re-use, recovery, and recycling of building envelope components and the circularity index of both the building envelope and its components. One of the most groundbreaking features is that each BIPV panel can be removed independently—a major advantage over conventional ventilated facades, where replacing a single module often requires disassembling larger facade sections. Each PV glass module is equipped with a security screw to prevent accidental dislodging. In the event of replacement or maintenance, the screw can be removed, allowing for easy detachment and reinstallation of the corresponding panel. Figure 8 reports a detail of the fixing system.

Figure 8: Detail of the fixing system of the BIPV module.

From an energy efficiency perspective, the installed photovoltaic system is designed to fully meet the annual electricity demand of the heat pumps used for apartment climate control.

Figure 9: Final illustration of the renovation building in the context (source: ISOLIFE srl).

The system will have a nominal peak power output ranging from 46 to 50 kWp, ensuring a renewable electricity supply. The total thermal energy demand of the heat pumps has been

conservatively estimated at 42,000 kWh (thermal), corresponding to an annual electricity consumption of approximately 14,000 kWh. The integrated BIPV facade system (Figure 9) is expected to generate around 15,000 kWh per year, effectively covering 100% of the annual electricity demand of the heat pumps. However, while the PV system ensures full annual coverage, it does not provide instantaneous self-consumption matching.

5 DISCUSSION

The renovation strategy presented in this study aims to bridge a critical gap in current European building renovation practices, which often prioritise energy efficiency while neglecting seismic safety. Indeed, the integration of structural and energy retrofitting is not only technically feasible but also necessary to ensure the long-term resilience and sustainability of the existing building stock, especially in seismic prone regions.

A key outcome of the case study is the demonstration of a low-impact, exterior-only structural intervention that significantly enhances the seismic performance of the building without requiring occupant relocation. The retrofit, focused on the reinforcement of 17 beam-column joints and 6 stairwell columns using CFRP composites, increased the seismic safety index (ζ_{SLV}) from 0.10 to 0.50. This result was achieved at a cost of approximately 66 €/m², which includes the structural retrofitting works and the restoration of affected external finishes.

From a technical perspective, the adoption of CFRP materials allowed for an efficient and localised strengthening solution with minimal intrusion. The use of externally anchored fibre-reinforced composites, applied with the need of minimal exterior demolition (infills), represents a significant advancement in reducing the social impact of seismic upgrades. Similarly, the column retrofitting design used a single wrap of CFRP strips, which restored shear capacity without exceeding concrete shear-compression limits. These solutions are aligned with the latest design guidelines and have been validated through both experimental and analytical studies.

The cost-effectiveness of the CFRP-based intervention strengthens the suitability of adopting targeted, local strengthening strategies in conjunction with envelope-level energy improvements.

Nonetheless, a full economic assessment of the renovation package must also account for the energy-related components, which include the prefabricated MPF system, hemp insulation, and BIPV glass modules. These elements, while increasing the upfront investment, contribute significantly to the long-term reduction in energy demand and operational costs. The MPF system, in particular, is designed for quick on-site installation, minimised waste, and disassembly at end-of-life — features that improve both construction logistics and life cycle performance. It must be considered that, at the moment, the components that constitute the MPF are prototypes under development to be tested in a real environment, not yet marketable. Unlike the seismic intervention, the costs of the facade's components, cannot currently be based on an industrialization process being still at the level of prototyping and development with technological readiness in TRL 7.

Additionally, the building-integrated photovoltaic system is projected to offset the entire electricity demand of the installed heat pumps, further improving the economic and environmental return on investment over the service life of the renovation.

From a policy standpoint, this integrated approach aligns closely with the objectives of the European Green Deal and the Renovation Wave Initiative. It supports the goals of decarbonising the building stock, improving housing conditions for vulnerable groups, and enhancing seismic resilience — a dimension often overlooked in large-scale renovation programmes. The demonstration of this methodology in a social housing context is particularly relevant, as it addresses one of the most sensitive sectors in terms of both safety and affordability.

The implementation of advanced monitoring systems and digital modelling (e.g., FEM and BIM integration) in the REHOUSE project will provide valuable insights into the long-term performance of the combined retrofitting strategy. Moreover, additional research is needed to optimise the coordination between structural and energy design, refine prefabrication processes, and improve the cost-efficiency of the MPF system, particularly as these technologies evolve towards full market readiness.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

This study presents a comprehensive and integrated renovation approach that combines seismic strengthening and energy efficiency improvements, specifically tailored for reinforced concrete social housing buildings in seismic-prone regions. The proposed methodology focuses on minimizing disruption to residents by implementing exterior-only interventions, such as the use of CFRP composites for local seismic upgrades and a prefabricated, modular multi-purpose facade (MPF) system that incorporates bio-based insulation and BIPV panels. The case study in Margherita di Savoia demonstrates the feasibility and cost-effectiveness of this strategy, achieving a fivefold increase in the seismic safety index at a competitive intervention cost of 66 €/m². Furthermore, the full coverage of annual energy demand for heat pumps is obtained through the BIPV system.

The synergy between structural and energy retrofitting proves essential for ensuring both life safety and environmental sustainability. Moreover, the project highlights the importance of using natural, recyclable materials and reversible fastening systems to enhance circularity and reduce the carbon footprint of renovations. While the current implementation focuses on a TRL7 demonstration, future developments will involve long-term performance monitoring under real operational conditions. These insights will be important to refining the methodology and promoting its scalability across the EU building stock. Upcoming efforts will also explore further standardisation, digital design integration (e.g., BIM-based workflows), and the potential extension of the intervention strategy to other building typologies and climatic contexts. Overall, this approach represents a viable and replicable model for advancing Europe's twin goals of seismic safety and energy transition, lowering the social impact.

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